

MODELS

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Models in cognitive and related sciences are part of an overarching methodology, *computational* or broadly *formal modelling*, that aims to test, refine, and showcase our understandings of brain, cognition, and behaviour.¹ In their foundational book *Models as Mediators*, Mary S. Morgan and Margaret Morrison (1999)² make the case that models play a mediatory role in science between what we observe and what we want to build to house our understandings, theories. Under this conception of models, known as the pragmatic view,³ we can carve out not only their unique role, but also why and how they must be protected from forces that do not prize understanding. Taking a broad perspective that sees all human activity that strives towards understanding as scientific or as under our purview as modellers, allows for this characterisation of models as mediators to be more generally fruitful.⁴ In the context of human-centred design, for example, our theories may be anything from our understanding of users' behaviours in a specific context to our understanding of what a user expects from a product or system a priori.

Importantly, scientific modelling is apart from other scientific praxis, such as concocting a verbal or formal theory or designing and running experiments.⁵ Models, as described by Morrison and Morgan,⁶ have the following characteristics:

- a. **construction** — models are neither directly derived from theory nor from data, but through an effortful friction between the modeller and the medium (e.g. their favourite programming language, mathematics, natural language) through which they are building their model;⁷

1. Frances Egan, *Deflating Mental Representation* (The MIT Press, March 2025), ISBN: 9780262381970, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/15666.001.0001>; Olivia Guest, "What Makes a Good Theory, and How Do We Make a Theory Good?," *Computational Brain & Behavior* 7, no. 4 (2024): 508–522, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-023-00193-2>; Iris van Rooij and Giosuè Baggio, "Theory Before the Test: How to Build High-Verisimilitude Explanatory Theories in Psychological Science," PMID: 33404356, *Perspectives on Psychological Science* 16, no. 4 (2021): 682–697, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620970604>.

2. Mary S. Morgan and Margaret Morrison, *Models as mediators: Perspectives on natural and social science*, 52 (Cambridge University Press, 1999).

3. Rasmus Grønfeldt Winther, "The Structure of Scientific Theories," in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Winter 2025, ed. Edward N. Zalta and Uri Nodelman (Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2025).

4. Also see: Nancy Cartwright, *How the laws of physics lie* (OUP Oxford, 1983); Catherine Z Elgin, *True enough* (MIT press, 2017).

5. The relationships between these are possibly traced using a path model (Olivia Guest and Andrea E Martin, "How computational modeling can force theory building in psychological science," *Perspectives on Psychological Science* 16, no. 4 [2021]: 789–802, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620970585>) or using related diagrammatic flows (Rooij and Baggio, "Theory Before the Test: How to Build High-Verisimilitude Explanatory Theories in Psychological Science").

6. Margaret Morrison and Mary S. Morgan, "Models as mediating instruments," in *Models as Mediators: Perspectives on Natural and Social Science*, ed. Mary S. Morgan and Margaret Morrison, Ideas in Context (Cambridge University Press, 1999), 10–37.

7. Richard P. Cooper and Olivia Guest, "Implementations are not specifications: Specification, replication and

- b. **functioning** — a model is like a tool insofar as it is, like a hammer, separate from both the nail (theory) and wall (observations, data) and indeed serves to connect, mediate between, the two;
- c. **representing** — successful models are “investigative devices for learning something [through] represent[ing] either some aspect of the world, or some aspect of our theories about the world, or both at once;”⁸
- d. **learning** — a model’s pedagogical and edificatory role is successfully played if and only if the modeller directly engages by building, modifying, bending, and even breaking the model.

Scientific-looking objects that carry the label ‘model’ but fail on the above can be rejected as actual models; and furthermore, can be assumed useless for the practice of improving understanding. An off-the-shelf model is thus irrelevant for the type of scientific reasoning we are interested in. As is an encounter that causes no modelling-related cognition, such as an interaction with software with no active model-building and -testing by the, now no more modeller but merely, user. It is the deep engagement with models in an effortful and methodical way that provides, although does not guarantee, the opportunity for refining theories. In other words, to deeply understand something about the world, we must understand our understanding using models.

In the contemporary entanglements with industry that scholarly fields find themselves — such as with the imposition of gargantuan statistical models, which consume breathtaking amounts of energy, and which require the building of evermore data-centres to house the glut of data unavoidably required for their so-called human-like abilities⁹ — the idea of using models in such slow¹⁰ ways is seemingly out the window. What is worthy of perseverating on in our specific context is not so much that so-called artificial intelligence (AI) models may harm our individual practice or displace our labour. They certainly may.¹¹ However, the threat from AI worthy of highlighting here is that a culture of frictionless practice, which such models (in name only) promote, is not only harmful to people’s mental health and skills, but also directly undermines scholarly praxis.¹²

Avoiding the effortful and difficult process of building, testing, and throwing away models — be they written in well-crafted code, be they not-yet-fully-formal models, or be they mock-ups of potential final products — with the goal of deeply understanding our theories about the world is anti-scientific and anti-scholarly. This spills over into an anti-intellectual stance for a designer or user of models. Such avoidance is normalised by the addictive convenience culture facilitated and entrenched by contemporary AI. A culture in which so-called prompting a machine for a seemingly polished output requires none of the above characteristics of modelling as a process. Furthermore, presenting anti- or non-scientific modelling endeavours as something other than what they are, may even veer into pseudo-science and pseudo-technology.¹³ To add insult to injury, if junior modellers are not trained to perform this praxis, the end of skills being inherited by future generations is nigh.

To subvert this, we must preserve the special status of crafting models. I propose this can be done in a two-pronged manoeuvre: a) rejection of the damaging culture, on the one

experimentation in computational cognitive modeling,” *Cognitive Systems Research* 27 (2014): 42–49, ISSN: 1389-0417, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsys.2013.05.001>; Olivia Guest, Andrea E. Martin, and Iris van Rooij, *On Models, Prediction, and Scientific Roles Thereof: Commentary on Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025)*, May 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19983695>; Peter Naur, “Programming as theory building,” *Microprocessing and microprogramming* 15, no. 5 (1985): 253–261.

8. Morrison and Morgan, “Models as mediating instruments,” p. 11.

9. Marcela Suarez Estrada et al., *Critical AI Literacy: Beyond hegemonic perspectives on sustainability*, June 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15677840>; Iris Van Rooij et al., “Reclaiming AI as a theoretical tool for cognitive science,” *Computational Brain & Behavior* 7, no. 4 (2024): 616–636.

10. Isabelle Stengers, *Another science is possible* (Polity Cambridge, UK, 2018).

11. Olivia Guest, “What Does ‘Human-Centred AI’ Mean?,” *Behavioral Sciences* 16, no. 4 (2026), ISSN: 2076-328X, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs16040583>.

12. Ishani Ray and Olivia Guest, *Contra Literacy-Laundering: Mechanistic Critical AI Literacy*, 2026.

13. Mel Andrews, Andrew Smart, and Abeba Birhane, “The reanimation of pseudoscience in machine learning and its ethical repercussions,” *Patterns* 5, no. 9 (2024); Päivi Seppälä and Ilmari Hirvonen, “Facial analysis AI as social pseudotechnology,” *European Journal for Philosophy of Science* 16, no. 2 (2026): 26.

hand; and on the other, *b*) thoughtful use of models with the characteristics above and that uphold Isabelle Stengers' slow science.¹⁴ To do the first is to cultivate what has been dubbed critical AI literacies,¹⁵ which can be seen as “the collection of ways of thinking about and relating to [AI] that rejects dominant frames presented by the technology industry, by naive computationalism, and by dehumanising ideologies.”¹⁶ This can comprise anything from writing polemical pieces to lobbying to rejection of creating and using such technologies.

An important form of high-level rejection is to push back against *correlationism*, which I use to mean the idea that because things can appear similar that therefore their unobservable properties must also match.¹⁷ My reflection in a mirror or a video of me may directly coincide with many of my outward appearances, but are neither me nor a valuable model of me — and relatedly, objects may act identically, but we may not be able to infer anything about the similarities of their internal components, think of a clockwork versus a digital timepiece.¹⁸ This becomes utterly damaging pedagogically when we assume the ‘output’ of an assignment, the essay or horrifically the grade, is the essence. The point is for students to engage with the subject matter and sharpen their writing skills such that they produce an argument the teacher can read. Just because an AI product can create an essay-shaped piece of text, indicates nothing about the ability of the learner, now reduced to the user of a product, to write. Worse, this frictionless technology blocks the user from learning opportunities, such as mentally modelling what the teacher may be asking, honing their theory of mind, dealing with feedback, as well as reading materials and digesting them. And worse still, the design of these technologies is addictive through weaponisation of the Eliza effect,¹⁹ people’s tendency to project human-likeness onto computational systems, and the Barnum-Forer effect,²⁰ the mistaken inference “that generic personality descriptions that could apply to anybody, applies uniquely to them.”²¹

The second way to push back is to make space for, by fortifying our and our mentees’ time for, by designing tools and environments that promote, the slow and steady praxis of modelling to explore our understandings and to generate *qualitative predictions*.²² A useful example to contrast quantitative versus qualitative prediction is our understanding of tides, which we explain by appealing to gravity.²³ However, there is no path from the highly accurate

14. Stengers, *Another science is possible*.

15. Andrea Baer, “When Is Critical AI Literacy Critical? Critical AI Literacy Discourse and Principles of Critical Pedagogy,” *Library Trends* 74, no. 4 (2026): 742–759; Lauren ME Goodlad, *Humanist in the Loop: Teaching Critical AI Literacies, Episode 1*, 1, 2025; Olivia Guest et al., “Against the Uncritical Adoption of AI Technologies in Academia,” 2025, Anuj Gupta et al., “Assistant, Parrot, or Colonizing Loudspeaker? ChatGPT Metaphors for Developing Critical AI Literacies,” *Open Praxis*, February 2024, <https://doi.org/10.55982/openpraxis.16.1.631>; Jennifer Sano-Franchini, “What’s ‘Critical’ about ‘Critical AI’? A Recommitment to Humanistic Inquiry in the Ostensible March to Hyper-Automation,” in *Proceedings of the Computers & Writing Conference* (2025), 6.

16. Olivia Guest, Marcela Suarez, and Iris van Rooij, *Towards critical artificial intelligence literacies*, 2025.

17. Guest, “What Does ‘Human-Centred AI’ Mean?”; Olivia Guest and Andrea E Martin, “A metatheory of classical and modern connectionism,” *Psychological Review*, 2026, Karl Marx, *Capital: volume III* (International Publishers, NY, 1894).

18. Olivia Guest, Mark Blokpoel, and Iris van Rooij, *What the Func? Multiple Realizability Need not be Vague*, April 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19388964>; Olivia Guest and Andrea E Martin, “On logical inference over brains, behaviour, and artificial neural networks,” *Computational Brain & Behavior* 6, no. 2 (2023): 213–227.

19. Sylvie Borau, “Deception, Discrimination, and Objectification: Ethical Issues of Female AI Agents: Deception, Discrimination, and Objectification: Ethical Issues of Female AI Agents,” *Journal of Business Ethics* 198, no. 1 (2025): 1–19; Sarah Dillon, “The Eliza effect and its dangers: from demystification to gender critique,” *Journal for Cultural Research* 24, no. 1 (2020): 1–15; Mayu Koike and Steve Loughnan, “Virtual relationships: Anthropomorphism in the digital age,” *Social and Personality Psychology Compass* 15, no. 6 (2021): e12603; Joseph Weizenbaum, “ELIZA—a computer program for the study of natural language communication between man and machine,” *Communications of the ACM* 9, no. 1 (1966): 36–45.

20. Baldur Bjarnason, “The LLMentalist Effect: How Chat-Based Large-Language-Models Replicate the Mechanisms of a Psychic’s Con,” *Out of the Software Crisis*, 2023, Paul E Meehl, “Wanted—a good cook-book,” *American Psychologist* 11, no. 6 (1956): 263; Kathleen D Vohs, *Barnum Effect*, 2016, <https://www.britannica.com/science/Barnum-Effect>.

21. Olivia Guest and Iris van Rooij, “Critical Artificial Intelligence Literacy for Psychologists,” 2025,

22. Guest and Martin, “How computational modeling can force theory building in psychological science”; Guest, Martin, and Rooij, *On Models, Prediction, and Scientific Roles Thereof: Commentary on Sanbonmatsu et al.* (2025).

23. Cartwright, *How the laws of physics lie*; Margaret Deacon, *Scientists and the sea, 1650–1900: a study of marine science* (Routledge, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315243610>; Elgin, *True enough*; Paul Hughes, “The revolution in tidal science,” *The Journal of Navigation* 59, no. 3 (2006): 445–459, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463306003870>.

quantitative predictions of the tides, which have been being refined over the millennia,²⁴ to the qualitative shift in explanation produced by carving out the concept of gravity. Quantitative predictions did not pile up to produce our contemporary understanding of gravity.

Protecting modelling praxis may be difficult, but needs must when the devil drives. The alternative is stifling our knowledge about (our understandings of) the world. And so to avoid making theorising and modelling seem superfluous, we must remember that scientific models do not operate like inferential statistical models wherein prediction is the goal. As expounded on above, models are the instrument through which we perform fully-fledged scientific reasoning on our theories, and which mediate between theory, formal or otherwise, connecting it to observations, data, and phenomena, and back again. A model (in name only) that is built through applying statistics over a dataset, which all contemporary artificial neural network-based AI models are, will neither function as mediator between data and theory — it has been contaminated — nor provide qualitative predictions.²⁵ Nor will it serve any user who seeks to gain insight and skills, nor any designer of systems who wishes for a society comprising such fellow humans.

Ultimately, “all science would be superfluous if the outward appearance and the essence of things directly coincided.”²⁶ If we merge essences and appearances in our reasoning, we risk our understandings of the world. All modelling, all metaphorical, theoretical, and mediatory thinking, enrich us and our societies and make possible not only valuable understandings of our own humanity, but constitute our humanity as such.

24. We have been creating qualitative predictions of the tides from at least Bede in the 8th century to Lord Kelvin’s the tide-predicting machines in the 19th, such as: William Thomson, “The tide gauge, tidal harmonic analyser, and tide predictor,” in *Minutes of the Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers*, vol. 65, 1881 (Thomas Telford-ICE Virtual Library, 1881), 2–25; Fath Wallis, *Bede, The Reckoning of Time* (Liverpool University Press, 1999), ISBN: 0853236933.

25. Guest and Martin, “A metatheory of classical and modern connectionism.”; Guest, Martin, and Rooij, *On Models, Prediction, and Scientific Roles Thereof: Commentary on Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025)*; Olivia Guest, Nancy Abigail Nuñez Hernández, and Mark Blokpoel, *Understanding Artificial Neural Networks: Mysterianism about Known Mechanism is Mysticism*, May 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20071869>.

26. Marx, *Capital: volume III*, p. 592.